

The Effect of Vibration on Mechanical, and Electrical Properties of Magnesium Silicide Composite Based Thermoelectric Modules

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Introduction

Thermoelectric module for automotive application^[1]

Factors affecting on TE modules in automobile

- Road excitation (< 200Hz)
 - Engine excitation
- $$f = Zn/30\tau$$
- f : Engine vibration frequency(Hz)
 Z : Number of engine cylinders
 n : Engine speed (r/min)
 τ : Number of piston strokes

The vibration frequency is ranging from 6.6 to 200 Hz^[2]

^[1]K. Shinohara et al., J. Jpn. Soc. Powder Powder Metallurgy 46 [5] 524-528 (1999)
^[2]G. Chen et al., J. ELECTRON MATER 43 [6] 1952-1958 (2014)
^[3]P. Marjamaa, et al., Proceedings of 2006 Electronic Components and Technology Conference 95-101 (2006)
^[4]G. Chen et al., J. ELECTRON MATER 43 [6] 1952-1958 (2014)

The cracking at the interface between Solder/Ni electrode^[3]

- Deformation by resonance
- Stress during the vibration test

To create more reliable module, we used thermoelectric composite material (Mg₂Si/SiC)

Objective

The evaluation of reliability for thermoelectric module using Mg₂Si/SiC composite

In the present study

- Shear test for TE module
- Vibration test for TE module
- Numerical simulation by FE analysis during vibration test

Material

Mg₂Si

Temperature : 1113 K Holding time : 15 min
 Atmosphere : Ar Pressure : 50 MPa

Mg₂Si/SiC

Mg₂Si: 99 vol% SiC: 1 vol%
 Temperature : 1113 K Holding time : 15 min
 Atmosphere : Ar Pressure : 50 MPa

Bonding condition

Interconnected material: Al Temperature : 923 K
 Holding time : 30 min Atmosphere : Air
 Pressure : 10 MPa

Experimental

Shear test

Experimental Study

[Test condition]
 Distance from terminal : 200 μm
 Displacement rate : 0.10 mm/s
 Bonding tester (PTR-1101)

Analysis

Stress analysis

Element	Hexahedron element, a point mass element
Mesh size	100 μm
Boundary condition	a point mass element: x=z=0, • 33 Hz, 90 m/s ² • 200 Hz, 200 m/s ² • 400 Hz, 400 m/s ²

Vibration test

Experimental Study

Frequency (Hz)	Acceleration speed (m/s ²)	Time (hour)
33	90	4
200	200	4
400	400	4

Vibration tester (ai210/SA1M)

Results & Discussion

Microstructure of Bonding layer

Shear Test

Bonding strength

Bonding strength : $\tau = P_{max}/A$
 Maximum load : P_{max}
 Bonding area : A

TE modules with high strength are fabricated

Al: $\tau = 14.6 \pm 7.5$ MPa

Fracture Surface

Failure occurs from Mg₂Si or interface between Mg₂Si/Ni. Interface failure between interconnected material and Ni was not observed

Vibration test

At no temperature difference

The electrical property doesn't change during vibration

Developed TE modules could endure dynamic vibration

Maximum principal stress of Mg₂Si is generated at 400Hz, 400m/s²
 ⇒ When conducting vibration with large acceleration, specimen is applied by large force

Maximum principal stress of Mg₂Si is Fabricated by Al: 0.07 MPa

Stress of Mg₂Si dose not exceed its strength during the vibration test

Mg₂Si of TE module can endure dynamic vibration

Conclusion

- ◆ From the microstructure observation of the interface, intermetallic compounds were formed, Mg₂Si/Ni and Ni/Al sheet were well bonded.
- ◆ From the shear strength test, failure of TE modules occurs from Mg₂Si, or interface between Mg₂Si/Ni.
- ◆ During the vibration test, the electrical resistance of the fabricated module did not change.
- ◆ Mg₂Si of TE module can endure dynamic vibration